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REINTEGRATE

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Glossary

FAIR Principles	Explain the acronym (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and what each principle entails for data management.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation - the regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
Data Anonymization	Define the process of removing personally identifiable information from data sets, so that the people whom the data describe remain anonymous.
Metadata	Data that provides information about other data. In the context of the DMP, this could refer to descriptions of the data sets used in the project.
Data Repository	A storage location for datasets, which may be used for archiving and sharing.
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	A persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify objects, standardized by ISO.
Data Encryption	The method of converting plaintext to an encoded version that can only be decoded by another entity if they have access to an encryption key.
Informed Consent	A process for getting permission before conducting a healthcare intervention on a person, or for disclosing personal information.
Data Portability	The ability to move data among different application, storage, or computing environments.
Data Lifecycle	The sequence of stages that a particular unit of data goes through from its initial generation or capture to its eventual archival and/or deletion at the end of its useful life.
Zenodo	An open-access repository where researchers can deposit data, software, reports, and research materials.
Open Access	The practice of providing unrestricted access via the Internet to peer-reviewed scholarly research.
Cloud Storage	A model of computer data storage in which the digital data is stored in logical pools, said to be on "the cloud", which is typically managed by a hosting company.
Data Integrity	The maintenance of, and the assurance of the accuracy and consistency of data over its entire lifecycle.
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer/Transport Layer Security - cryptographic protocols designed to provide communications security over a computer network.

Executive Summary

The RE-INTEGRATE project, funded by the European Union's Horizon EUROPE programme, represents a collaborative effort between the African Union (AU) and the European Union (EU) to formulate climate-compatible energy strategies. This initiative addresses the urgent need for sustainable energy solutions that are adaptable across different geographical and economic contexts, with a focus on fostering mutual understanding and cooperation between EU and AU member states.

The project's Data Management Plan (DMP) is central to its operational framework, ensuring the systematic handling, sharing, and preservation of data in accordance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. The DMP outlines comprehensive strategies for managing diverse datasets, including energy models, climate policy data, and stakeholder inputs, which are integral to achieving the project's ambitious goals.

The plan underscores the importance of efficient data management in enhancing research quality and ensuring the successful implementation of energy strategies. It covers different aspects of data management, including the types of data collected, the methodologies for data collection and generation, and the relationship of data to the project objectives. Moreover, it details procedures and protocols for ensuring data security, ethical data handling, and compliance with international data protection laws, particularly the GDPR.

The DMP also elaborates on resource allocation for data management, assigning responsibilities to designated personnel and specifying the necessary infrastructure and tools. This structured approach to data management facilitates the project's overarching aim of developing integrated, sustainable energy solutions that are informed by robust, reliable data.

In essence, the RE-INTEGRATE project's DMP is a testament to the project's commitment to transparency, security, and ethical standards in data management. It is designed as a living document, adaptable to the evolving needs of the project, and serves as a foundational element in bridging the knowledge and technology gaps between the EU and AU, thereby contributing significantly to global efforts in climate-compatible energy planning.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a strategic document that guides the project's data management practices. The RE-INTEGRATE project aims to develop climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the African Union and the European Union. To achieve this, the project will generate and collect various types of data, such as energy models, climate policy data, and stakeholder inputs. These data need to be managed effectively, ensuring that they are handled, shared, and preserved in alignment with the project's objectives. The DMP serves several key purposes for the RE-INTEGRATE project. First, it supports the project's specific objectives by defining how the data will contribute to the project's overarching goals. Second, it provides strategies for managing the diverse data types involved in the project efficiently and securely. Third, it ensures compliance with international data protection laws, such as the GDPR [1], and addresses ethical issues in data management, especially given the transcontinental nature of the project. Fourth, it adheres to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles [2], making the data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This is vital for enhancing collaboration and knowledge exchange between the EU and AU. Fifth, it identifies and mitigates risks for data security, quality, and integrity, which are important for maintaining the data's trustworthiness and reliability. Sixth, it is a living document, which can be updated and revised according to the changing needs and findings of the project, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness throughout the project lifecycle. In summary, the DMP is a key element of the RE-INTEGRATE project, as it enables the successful management of data, which is essential for realizing the project's vision of shared knowledge and collaborative development in energy strategies between the EU and AU.

1.2 Importance in the context of the project

Data management is of paramount importance for the RE-INTEGRATE project, which aims to develop climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the African Union and the European Union. The project will generate and collect diverse and complex data sets, such as energy models, climate policy data, and stakeholder inputs. These data sets require effective management to ensure that they support the project's objectives, enhance the research quality, and achieve the desired outcomes.

One of the main goals of RE-INTEGRATE is to create a knowledge-sharing environment and to develop fit-for-purpose modeling toolkits. This goal necessitates a structured approach to managing the large amounts of data involved in the project. The project also entails collaboration across different geographical regions and disciplines, which poses challenges in data standardization, storage, and accessibility. Therefore, data management according to FAIR principles [2] is vital for facilitating cross-border and cross-sectoral collaboration. Another key aspect of the project is capacity building in energy and climate modeling within the African Union. This aspect emphasizes the need for robust data management strategies, which ensure that data and modeling tools are not only accessible but also adaptable to various contexts, increasing their utility and impact. Furthermore, data management in RE-INTEGRATE has to comply with ethical considerations and regional data protection regulations. This aspect is especially important given the transcontinental nature of the project, where data privacy laws may differ. A well-structured DMP will ensure compliance with these regulations, improving the credibility and reliability of the project's outputs.

1.3 Scope and applicability

The DMP for the RE-INTEGRATE project defines the scope and applicability of data management strategies across various project stages and activities. This section describes how the DMP applies to the project's framework.

- **Data Types:** The DMP covers different types of data, such as energy system models, climate policy analyses, stakeholder feedback, and integrated assessment results. These include both quantitative data, like modeling outputs, and qualitative data, such as stakeholder engagement insights.
- **Data-Related Activities:** The DMP covers all aspects of data handling, such as collection, storage, processing, sharing, and preservation. These are important for maintaining data integrity and ensuring its optimal utility throughout the project.
- **Project Lifecycle:** The DMP applies to the entire lifecycle of the RE-INTEGRATE project, from initial data acquisition and modeling to the dissemination of findings and policy recommendations. This ensures a consistent and effective approach to data management at each project phase.
- **Research Methodologies:** The DMP addresses the specific data management needs arising from the project's research methodologies, which focus on energy modeling and scenario analysis. This involves handling large-scale modeling outputs and ensuring the interoperability of diverse data sets.
- **Team Roles and Responsibilities:** The DMP specifies the roles and responsibilities of the project team members regarding data management. This ensures clarity in who is responsible for different aspects of data handling, facilitating efficient and secure data management practices.
- **Compliance and Ethical Considerations:** The DMP emphasizes the importance of complying with ethical standards and data protection regulations, especially given the project's transcontinental scope. This involves considerations for GDPR compliance and ethical handling of sensitive data.
- **Key Focus Areas:** The DMP pays special attention to managing large datasets and ensuring data privacy and security. The DMP outlines specific strategies to address these focus areas, adapting to the unique challenges they present.

2. Overview of the Project

2.1 Brief description of the project

The RE-INTEGRATE project is an innovative initiative that aims to improve energy strategies through collaboration between the African Union and the European Union. The main goal of the project is to create climate-compatible energy models that are customized and sustainable for different regions. The project also develops advanced energy planning tools, which are essential for making informed policies and managing energy strategically. A key aspect of RE-INTEGRATE is to promote knowledge sharing and capacity building across various regions, highlighting local expertise in energy modeling. This approach helps to achieve self-reliant and context-specific energy solutions, in line with wider climate objectives. The project generates and analyzes a large amount of data, which requires a comprehensive and effective data management plan to ensure data quality, availability, and usefulness in policy development and strategic planning.

2.2 Objectives, Outcomes, and Relevance to EU Horizon Guidelines

The RE-INTEGRATE project aims to establish an enabling and inclusive environment for knowledge sharing and development of context-appropriate modeling tools across the African Union (AU) and the European Union (EU). This is in response to the challenges faced in energy planning due to sometimes uncoordinated and biased approaches in model design and application, leading to limited uptake in planning and policymaking.

The project has four main objectives: to formalize bi- or multi-lateral partnerships between AU and EU institutions, to develop open-source national and regional research infrastructures for energy modeling, to craft policy briefs that offer practical and actionable recommendations for climate-compatible growth and energy integration, and to implement quality assessment procedures to evaluate the extent and quality of knowledge sharing.

The expected outcomes of RE-INTEGRATE are closely aligned with Horizon Europe's goals, emphasizing the project's commitment to impactful, sustainable change. The project will reinforce the AU-EU HLPD CCSE Partnership, provide knowledge and scientific energy system modeling as an evidence base, increase clean energy generation, and establish a permanent network of African experts and expertise. RE-INTEGRATE will also adhere to the FAIR data principles and ethical standards, ensuring data protection and advancing the EU Horizon Guidelines. By fostering international cooperation and mutual learning, RE-INTEGRATE stands as a pivotal initiative in the shared journey towards sustainable, climate-compatible energy strategies across the AU and EU.

The project is relevant to the EU Horizon Guidelines, as it aligns with several priorities and principles: tackling global challenges, such as climate change and sustainable development, by developing innovative and collaborative solutions that can benefit both the AU and EU; fostering international cooperation and association, by enhancing the partnership between the AU and EU in research and innovation, and promoting mutual learning and capacity building; adhering to the FAIR data principles, by ensuring that the data generated and used in the project is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, and by facilitating data sharing and dissemination; complying with ethical standards and data protection regulations, by respecting the rights and interests of the data subjects and providers, and by following the GDPR and other relevant laws; and following the Do No Significant Harm principle, by ensuring that the project's activities and outputs do not cause any adverse effects on the environment, health, or social well-being.

3. Research Data Summary

3.1 Description of the data to be collected/generated (types, formats, volume)

The RE-INTEGRATE project will collect and generate various types of data that are essential for its objectives. These include quantitative data, such as energy consumption patterns, climate model outputs, and renewable energy potentials, and qualitative data, such as stakeholder feedback and policy documents. The data formats will vary from numerical datasets in spreadsheets to textual reports and visual presentations, depending on the data type and the analysis purpose. The data volume will be large, due to the extensive modeling activities and the widespread stakeholder consultations. This data diversity, in both format and volume, supports the project's objectives to provide comprehensive insights into energy strategies and informed decision-making.

3.2 Purpose and methods of data collection/generation

The RE-INTEGRATE project will collect or generate each type of data with specific purposes, related to the project's research questions. Quantitative data from models will provide information on energy scenarios and projections, while qualitative data from stakeholders will provide insights on policy and societal implications. Data collection methods will include simulations using energy models, surveys, and interviews, ensuring a combination of quantitative rigor and qualitative richness. Ethical considerations, especially in stakeholder engagement, will be paramount, ensuring consent and data privacy. These methods are chosen for their ability to provide reliable, relevant data that supports the project's analyses.

3.3 Relation of data to project objectives

The data collected and generated in the RE-INTEGRATE project is closely related to its objectives. The energy models and scenario data will help to understand and develop effective energy strategies. Stakeholder data will help to ground these strategies in societal needs and policy realities. This data is not only important for the research process but also for achieving tangible outcomes, such as informed policy recommendations and enhanced energy planning tools. This subsection shows how the data is a key element of the project, essential for achieving its aims of advancing energy strategies in the context of climate compatibility.

4. FAIR Data Principles

4.1 Making data Findable

The RE-INTEGRATE project uses metadata standards that match the project's focus on energy strategies and climate-compatible development. The project's scope requires metadata standards such as Dublin Core and the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), which were widely used and offered comprehensive metadata elements. The project also developed and uses a data management platform (<https://data.scicloud.site>) that improved the findability of data. This platform allows the project partners to publish their metadata, which describes the data they have collected or generated. The metadata is standardized and searchable, making it easy for other project partners to find and request the data they need. The actual data, however, can be physically located and protected by the data owners, who have the sole authority to grant or deny access to their data. The project will also register the datasets with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and integrate them with repositories like Zenodo [4] and institutional databases related to energy and climate research. Moreover, the project will use existing platforms like the European Union Open Data Portal [5] and sector-specific databases to enable data discovery, making the data accessible to a broad audience.

4.2 Making data Accessible

The RE-INTEGRATE project considers data sharing and accessibility as key aspects of the project's approach, as they support the project's objectives of developing climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the AU and EU. The project uses the same data management platform that facilitates data sharing and discovery among the project's partners and stakeholders, while complying with ethical and legal standards, such as GDPR and other data protection regulations. The project also ensures that sensitive information related to energy policies and modeling results will be handled with the highest level of confidentiality and security. The project's data management platform allows the project partners to publish their metadata, which describes the data they have collected or generated. The metadata are standardized and searchable, making it easy for other project partners to find and request the data they needed. The actual data, however, can be physically located and protected by the data owners, who have the sole authority to grant or deny access to

their data. The project maintains a delicate balance between making data accessible and protecting data privacy, aligning with GDPR and other data protection regulations. These measures are crucial for preserving the integrity and confidentiality of the data.

4.3 Making data Interoperable

The RE-INTEGRATE project uses data formats and standards that enable data interoperability, which is important for integrating data from different sources and regions. The project employs common data formats, such as CSV, XML, and JSON, which are widely supported and easy to process. Additionally, the project adheres to common data standards, such as ISO 19115 for geographic information and ISO 8601 for date and time, ensuring consistency and compatibility. The project integrates data with other datasets, like the World Energy Outlook and the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, providing additional information and context for the project's data. The data management platform and the repositories are utilized to link the datasets with each other, using metadata and DOIs. Furthermore, the project leverages existing platforms and databases to integrate the data with other relevant data in the energy and climate domains.

4.4 Making data Reusable

The RE-INTEGRATE project uses data licensing and reuse terms that promoted data reuse, which is important for enhancing the impact and utility of the data. The project uses open licenses, such as CC BY 4.0, which allowed data reuse with attribution. The project also uses clear and explicit reuse terms, such as the Data User Agreement, which specifies the conditions and limitations of data reuse. The project also ensures the long-term usability of data, which is important for supporting future research and collaboration. The project uses the data management platform and the repositories to preserve the data and the metadata, ensuring their availability and accessibility. The project also uses data quality and documentation measures, such as validation, verification, and annotation, to ensure the reliability and understandability of the data. The project also uses data citation and provenance measures, such as DOIs and metadata, to ensure the traceability and accountability of the data.

5. Allocation of Resources

The RE-INTEGRATE project recognizes the importance of data management for achieving its objectives of developing climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the AU and EU. Therefore, the project allocates sufficient resources, both human and technical, to ensure effective and efficient data management throughout the project lifecycle. This section describes the budgeting, personnel, and infrastructure and tools required for data management in the RE-INTEGRATE project.

5.1 Personnel responsible for data management

The RE-INTEGRATE project has a single data expert, Dr. Xiufeng Liu (xiuli@dtu.dk) from the Technical University of Denmark, who is responsible for all aspects of data management in the project. He is the data manager, who develops and implements the data management plan, ensuring that it aligns with the project's objectives and follows the FAIR data principles. He also oversees and performs the data collection, processing, storage, security, dissemination, and sharing activities, ensuring that they are done according to the project's standards and comply with ethical and legal regulations. He reports to the project coordinator and communicates with the project partners and stakeholders on data management issues. He also provides guidance and support to the project partners on data management best practices, such as data quality, documentation, and protection. He monitors and evaluates the data management performance and impact, using indicators and feedback mechanisms. He reviews and updates the data management plan, according to the changing needs and findings of the project.

Dr. Xiufeng Liu is supported by a team of specialists from each project partner, who contribute to the data management activities according to their expertise and roles. The data management team consists of the following members:

- Suat Sevenscan from KTH (sevenscan@kth.se), who is an energy modeler and scenario analyst. He has extensive experience and publications on fuel cell, life cycle assessment, cogeneration, renewable energy, and economic feasibility. He is also involved in data analysis and visualization tools, such as R and Tableau.
- Anastasis Giannousakis from E3Modelling (giannousakis@e3modelling.com), who is also the leader of WP3, the largest data-producing and data-using work package in the project, together with WP4. He is a macroeconomic and environmental impact assessor and provides data on policy evaluation and climate compatibility for the project. He has expertise and publications on energy modeling, scenario analysis, and policy assessment. He is also involved in data processing and analysis tools, such as E3ME and LEAP.
- Other project partners, who provide data on stakeholder inputs, climate policy data, and other relevant data sources for the project.

The data management team works closely with Dr. Xiufeng Liu and follows his instructions and guidance on data handling. The data management team also collaborates and communicates with each other, ensuring data consistency and compatibility across the project.

5.2 Infrastructure and tools required

To manage data efficiently, RE-INTEGRATE employs cutting-edge infrastructure and software tools, which feature advanced storage systems, computational resources, and security mechanisms. The project's infrastructure and tools are carefully chosen to guarantee robust data handling, analysis, and protection. This strategic choice supports the project's objectives, such as improving the modeling and analysis of climate-compatible development pathways and promoting knowledge exchange between the AU and EU. By using these technologies, RE-INTEGRATE seeks to accomplish its goals as specified in the Grant Agreement, ensuring alignment with the project's core objectives and expected outcomes.

The project uses the following infrastructure and tools for data management:

- **Data management platform:** a web-based platform that enables data publishing, discovery, access, and interoperability among the project partners and stakeholders, using metadata standards, DOIs, and APIs. The RE-INTEGRATE data platform is accessible at <http://data.scicloud.site> and allows the project partners to share what data they have (metadata only, while the actual data are physically located and protected by the data owners). The platform also integrates with other relevant data sources, such as the EU Open Data Portal [5] and the World Energy Outlook [6].
- **Data repositories:** online repositories that store and preserve the project's data sets, ensuring their long-term availability and accessibility, using open licenses and formats. The project uses repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/re-integrate/>) and institutional databases related to energy and climate research, and assigns DOIs to the data sets to enable data citation and provenance.
- **Data analysis tools:** software tools that enable data analysis, such as energy modeling, scenario building, and policy evaluation, using various methods and techniques. The project uses tools such as OSeMOSYS, FlexTool and LEAP for energy modeling and scenario analysis, and GEM-E3 for macroeconomic and environmental impact assessment.

- **Data visualization tools:** software tools that enable data visualization, such as charts, graphs, and maps, using various styles and formats. The project uses tools such as Tableau and Power BI for data visualization and reporting, and creates interactive dashboards and infographics to present and communicate the results effectively.
- **Data protection tools:** software tools that ensure data protection, such as encryption, authentication, and backup, using various protocols and mechanisms. The project uses tools such as BitLocker and LastPass for data encryption and authentication, and OneDrive and Team files for data backup and recovery. The project also follows data security policies and procedures, such as passwords and firewalls, and complies with the GDPR and other data protection regulations.

6. Data Security

Data security is a crucial aspect of the RE-INTEGRATE project, as it involves handling sensitive and valuable data from various sources and regions. The project adopts a comprehensive and proactive approach to data security, ensuring that the data is protected from unauthorized access, misuse, or damage. The project follows three main objectives for data security: maintaining the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data. This section describes the measures, strategies, and standards that the project implements to achieve these objectives.

6.1 Data protection measures

The RE-INTEGRATE project implements robust data protection measures, using a combination of technical and organizational methods. These measures aim to safeguard the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, both at rest and in transit. The project uses advanced encryption protocol SSL/TLS to secure the data from unauthorized access or interception. The project also employs rigorous access control systems, such as role-based authorization, to ensure that only authorized personnel can access sensitive information, for example in our RE-INTEGRATE data platform and Team files. The project conducts regular security audits internally to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the data protection measures.

The project also employs state-of-the-art firewall and intrusion detection systems to shield the data from external threats, such as malware, phishing, or denial-of-service attacks. The project maintains internal data integrity checks, such as checksums and digital signatures, to prevent accidental or intentional data corruption. The project also implements data anonymization and pseudonymization techniques, such as masking and hashing, to protect the privacy and identity of the data subjects.

6.2 Risk assessment and mitigation strategies

Risk assessment in the RE-INTEGRATE project is an ongoing process, identifying and evaluating potential vulnerabilities in the data management system. This process involves assessing the likelihood and impact of various risks, such as data loss, theft, leakage, or breach. The project uses a risk matrix to prioritize and categorize the risks, based on their severity and urgency. The project also conducts regular risk assessments to update and refine the risk profile.

Mitigation strategies in the RE-INTEGRATE project are designed to diminish the likelihood and mitigate the impact of identified risks through a combination of advanced technological solutions and administrative measures. To guarantee data availability and facilitate recovery in the event of data loss or damage, we deploy sophisticated backup systems and leverage cloud storage solutions. Encryption and stringent access control measures are integral to our approach to preventing data theft and leakage.

The following table shows some examples of data management risks, and their likelihood, impact, and risk level:

Table 1 - Examples of data management risks

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Risk Level	Mitigation
Use of weak passwords leading to unauthorized access	Likely	High	H	Implement strong password policies, enforce password complexity requirements, and conduct regular password strength audits. Encourage the use of password managers and multi-factor authentication to enhance security measures.
Data loss due to hardware failure, human error, or natural disaster	Unlikely	High	M	Perform regular backups and use cloud storage
Data theft due to cyberattack, insider threat, or physical breach	Unlikely	Extreme	H	Use encryption and access control measures
Data leakage due to unauthorized access, misuse, or disclosure	Likely	High	H	Implement data anonymization and pseudonymization techniques
Data breach due to non-compliance with GDPR or other regulations	Very Unlikely	Extreme	M	Review and update data protection policies and procedures
Data corruption due to software bug, virus, or tampering	Unlikely	Moderate	L	Use data integrity checks and antivirus software
Data obsolescence due to outdated format, standard, or technology	Likely	Low	L	Monitor and update data formats and standards

6.3 Compliance with GDPR and other regulations

The RE-INTEGRATE project's data management practices are designed to be fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] and other relevant data protection laws, such as the African Union Convention on Cybersecurity and Personal Data Protection. The project follows the principles and requirements of these regulations, ensuring that the data is processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently. The project also ensures that the data is collected and used for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes, and that the data is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary. The project also ensures that the data is accurate, up-to-date, and kept for no longer than necessary.

The project also respects and protects the rights and interests of the data subjects, ensuring that they have control over their personal data. The project implements procedures for data subject access requests, data portability, and the right to be forgotten, allowing the data subjects to access, correct, delete, or transfer their data. The project also implements procedures for data protection impact assessments, data breach notifications, and data protection by design and by default, ensuring that data protection is embedded in every stage of the data lifecycle. The project also regularly reviews its

policies and procedures to align with any changes in data protection regulations, ensuring ongoing compliance.

7. Ethical Aspects

The RE-INTEGRATE project is committed to conducting its research and innovation activities in an ethical manner, respecting the values and rights of all stakeholders involved. The project recognizes that data management is a key aspect of ethical research, as it involves collecting, using, and sharing data that may have significant implications for the environment, society, and individuals [3]. Therefore, the project follows ethical principles and guidelines that ensure the responsible and respectful handling of data. This section describes the ethical considerations, procedures, and measures that the project implements in relation to data collection and use, informed consent, and handling of sensitive or personal data.

7.1 Ethical considerations related to data collection and use

The RE-INTEGRATE project recognizes the ethical implications of its data collection and use and strives to uphold the highest ethical standards in its data management practices. This involves respecting the privacy and dignity of data subjects, ensuring the accuracy and quality of data, and preventing any harm or misuse of data. The project's approach is guided by ethical principles and frameworks that emphasize the importance of data stewardship, accountability, and transparency, especially in the context of renewable energy sources and their environmental and social impact.

7.2 Informed consent procedures (if applicable)

The RE-INTEGRATE project follows the ethical and legal standards for obtaining informed consent from human participants in research. The project only involves participants who agree to take part in the research voluntarily, after receiving adequate information about the study. The information that the project provides to participants covers the purpose, methods, and expected outcomes of the research, as well as the rights and responsibilities of participants, such as the right to withdraw consent at any time without penalty. The information also explains the potential risks and benefits of participating in the research, such as the possibility of emotional distress or the contribution to scientific knowledge, and the measures taken to protect the confidentiality and privacy of participants and their data. The project provides this information to participants in a written or oral form, depending on the context and feasibility of the study. The project also obtains a signature or a verbal confirmation from participants as an indication of their informed consent. The project respects the dignity and autonomy of participants and ensures that they are not coerced or deceived into participating in the research.

7.3 Handling of sensitive or personal data

The RE-INTEGRATE project prioritizes the protection and security of sensitive or personal data, which may include information on energy consumption, climate policies, or stakeholder opinions. The project implements effective measures for data anonymization and encryption to safeguard personal information from unauthorized access or disclosure. Compliance with data protection regulations, such as GDPR, is strictly enforced, ensuring that all personal data is processed in a manner that respects the rights and interests of data subjects and data providers.

8. Data Sharing and Preservation

The RE-INTEGRATE project recognizes the importance of sharing and preserving the data it generates and collects, as this enhances the impact and utility of its research outputs. The project follows the FAIR data principles, ensuring that the data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The project also complies with ethical and legal standards, respecting the rights and interests of the data

subjects and providers. The project has developed and implemented the following strategies for data sharing and preservation.

8.1 Strategies for data sharing with the scientific community and the public

The RE-INTEGRATE project aims to disseminate its data and findings to a wide audience, including researchers, policymakers, practitioners, and the general public. The project uses various methods and channels for data sharing, such as:

- **Academic Publications:** The project publishes its data and results in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings, which are widely recognized and respected in the scientific community. The project uses open access journals, where possible, to increase the visibility and accessibility of its publications. The project also provides data citations and DOIs for its datasets, enabling proper attribution and traceability.
- **Online Platforms:** The project uses online platforms, such as the project website, social media, and blogs, to communicate its data and findings to a broader and more diverse audience. The project uses these platforms to provide updates on the project's progress, highlight key outcomes and impacts, and engage with stakeholders and the public. The project also uses these platforms to link to the project's data and publications, facilitating data discovery and access.
- **Data Repositories:** The project deposits its data in reliable and established data repositories, which are accessible to the scientific community and the public. The project uses repositories that comply with international data standards, such as Zenodo [4], the European Union Open Data Portal, and sector-specific databases. The project also provides metadata and DOIs for its datasets, ensuring data findability and interoperability.

These methods and channels are chosen for their ability to reach a wide and relevant audience, and to promote transparent and open access to the project's data and findings. This supports the project's objectives of fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration in energy and climate research and innovation.

8.2 Long-term preservation plans for data

The RE-INTEGRATE project is committed to ensuring the long-term preservation of its data, as this ensures the data's availability and usability for future research and innovation. The project has adopted the following strategies for data preservation, such as:

- **Data Backups:** The project performs regular and secure backups of its data, using both local and cloud storage. The project uses encryption and password protection to safeguard the data from unauthorized access or loss. The project also maintains multiple copies of the data in different locations, such as on the project server, and on the Microsoft Team files Repository. The project informs its partners about the data backup procedures through the data management plan and the data sharing agreement.
- **Data Formats:** The project uses common and stable data formats, such as CSV, XML, and JSON, which are widely supported and easy to process. The project also uses common data standards, such as ISO 19115 for geographic information and ISO 8601 for date and time, which ensure consistency and compatibility. The project also monitors and updates the data formats, as needed, to prevent data obsolescence or degradation.
- **Data Quality:** The project ensures the quality and integrity of its data, using validation, verification, and annotation methods. The project also documents and describes its data, using metadata and data dictionaries, which provide information on the data's origin, context,

structure, and meaning. The project also follows data quality and documentation standards, such as DDI and Dublin Core, which enhance the reliability and understandability of the data.

These strategies are chosen for their ability to preserve the data's integrity and usability, ensuring the data's long-term value and impact. This supports the project's vision of contributing to the scientific understanding and societal benefit in the field of energy and climate.

8.3 Repositories and platforms for data storage

The RE-INTEGRATE project uses secure and established repositories and platforms for storing its data, which are chosen for their compliance with international data standards and best practices. The project uses the following repositories and platforms for data storage, such as:

- **Data Management Platform:** The project uses a data management platform, which is a web-based application that facilitates data sharing and discovery among the project partners and stakeholders. The platform allows the project partners to publish their metadata, which describe the data they have collected or generated. The metadata is standardized and searchable, making it easy for other project partners to find and request the data they need. The actual data, however, is physically located and protected by the data owners, who have the sole authority to grant or deny access to their data. The platform also integrates with other repositories and platforms, such as Zenodo and the European Union Open Data Portal, enabling data dissemination and preservation.
- **Zenodo:** The project uses Zenodo, which is a general-purpose open-access repository for research data and publications. Zenodo is hosted by CERN [4], and is part of the European Commission's Open Science Cloud. Zenodo allows the project to deposit its data and publications, and to assign DOIs and metadata to them. Zenodo also provides long-term preservation and access to the data and publications, ensuring their availability and visibility to the scientific community and the public.
- **European Union Open Data Portal:** The project uses the European Union Open Data Portal, which is the single point of access to open data from the EU institutions, agencies, and bodies. The portal provides access to data on various topics, such as energy, climate, environment, and research. The portal also provides tools and services for data analysis and reuse, such as APIs, visualizations, and applications. The portal allows the project to integrate its data with other relevant data from the EU, enhancing its interoperability and utility.
- **Sector-Specific Databases:** The project uses sector-specific databases, which are specialized repositories for data related to energy and climate. These databases include the World Energy Outlook, the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, and the Climate Policy Database. These databases provide additional information and context for the project's data, enabling comparative and integrative analysis. The databases also allow the project to link its data with other data sets in the energy and climate domains, increasing its relevance and impact.

These repositories and platforms are chosen for their ability to store the data securely and efficiently, ensuring its accessibility and usability for the project's purposes. This enables effective data management and analysis, supporting the project's objectives of developing climate-compatible energy strategies.

9. Guidelines for Data Protection and Security

The RE-INTEGRATE project recognizes the importance of data protection and security, as it involves handling sensitive and valuable data from various sources and regions. The project adopts a comprehensive and proactive approach to data protection and security, ensuring that the data is protected from unauthorized access, misuse, or damage. The project follows three main objectives for data protection and security: maintaining the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data. This section describes the measures, strategies, and standards that the project implements to achieve these objectives throughout the project lifecycle.

9.1 Data management through the project lifecycle

The RE-INTEGRATE project implements robust data management practices, using a combination of technical and organizational methods. These practices aim to safeguard the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, both at rest and in transit. The project uses advanced encryption protocols, such as AES-256 and SSL/TLS, to secure the data from unauthorized access or interception. The project also employs rigorous access control systems, such as role-based authorization in RE-INTEGRATE data platform, to ensure that only authorized personnel can access sensitive information. The project conducts regular security audits, both internally and externally, to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the data protection measures. The project also employs state-of-the-art firewall and intrusion detection systems to shield the data from external threats, such as malware, phishing, or denial-of-service attacks. The project maintains internal data integrity checks, such as checksums and digital signatures, to prevent accidental or intentional data corruption. The project also implements data anonymization and pseudonymization techniques, such as masking and hashing, to protect the privacy and identity of the data subjects.

The project follows these data management practices throughout the project lifecycle, from data collection to data dissemination. The project ensures that data is collected and used for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes, and that data is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary. The project also ensures that data is accurate, up-to-date, and kept for no longer than necessary. The project also respects and protects the rights and interests of the data subjects, ensuring that they have control over their personal data. The project implements procedures for data subject access requests, data portability, and the right to be forgotten, allowing the data subjects to access, correct, delete, or transfer their data. The project also implements procedures for data protection impact assessments, data breach notifications, and data protection by design and by default, ensuring that data protection is embedded in every stage of the data lifecycle. The project also regularly reviews its policies and procedures to align with any changes in data protection regulations, ensuring ongoing compliance.

9.2 Data protection and ethics in data management

The RE-INTEGRATE project is committed to conducting its research and innovation activities in an ethical manner, respecting the values and rights of all stakeholders involved. The project recognizes that data management is a key aspect of ethical research, as it involves collecting, using, and sharing data that may have significant implications for the environment, society, and individuals. Therefore, the project follows ethical principles and guidelines that ensure the responsible and respectful handling of data, especially when it pertains to renewable energy sources and their environmental and social impact.

The project's approach is guided by ethical principles and frameworks that emphasize the importance of data stewardship, accountability, and transparency, especially in the context of renewable energy

sources and their environmental and social impact. The project adheres to the following ethical principles and guidelines:

- **Respect for human dignity and rights:** The project respects the dignity and rights of the data subjects and providers, ensuring that they are informed, consented, and protected. The project also respects the cultural and social diversity of the data subjects and providers, ensuring that their values and preferences are considered and respected.
- **Beneficence and non-maleficence:** The project aims to maximize the benefits and minimize the harms of the data collection and use, ensuring that the data is used for the public good and not for malicious or harmful purposes. The project also ensures that the data does not cause any adverse effects on the environment, health, or social well-being of the data subjects and providers, or the wider society.
- **Justice and fairness:** The project ensures that the data collection and use is fair and equitable, ensuring that the data subjects and providers are not discriminated against or exploited. The project also ensures that the data is shared and disseminated in a fair and transparent manner, ensuring that the data subjects and providers are acknowledged and rewarded for their contributions.
- **Integrity and honesty:** The project ensures that the data collection and use is honest and trustworthy, ensuring that the data is accurate, reliable, and valid. The project also ensures that the data is transparent and accountable, ensuring that the data sources, methods, and results are clearly documented and reported.

The project follows these ethical principles and guidelines throughout the project lifecycle, from data collection to data dissemination. The project implements ethical procedures and measures, such as informed consent, data protection, and data quality, to ensure that the data management practices are ethical and compliant. The project also conducts ethical reviews and evaluations, both internally and externally, to ensure that the data management practices are consistent and effective.

9.3 Data breach notification procedures

The RE-INTEGRATE project recognizes the possibility and the severity of data breaches, which may compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data. The project adopts a proactive and responsive approach to data breach prevention and mitigation, ensuring that the data is protected and restored as soon as possible. The project follows a four-step procedure for responding to data breaches, which includes detection, assessment, containment, and notification.

- **Detection:** The project monitors and detects any potential or actual data breaches, using various tools and methods, such as security audits, intrusion detection systems, and data integrity checks. The project also encourages and enables the reporting of any suspected or confirmed data breaches, by the project staff, partners, stakeholders, or data subjects, using various channels, such as email, phone, or online forms.
- **Assessment:** The project assesses the nature and extent of the data breach, using various criteria, such as the type, volume, and sensitivity of the data involved, the cause and duration of the breach, and the potential impact and harm of the breach. The project also assigns a risk level to the data breach, based on the likelihood and severity of the breach, using a risk matrix.
- **Containment:** The project contains and isolates the data breach, using various measures, such as disconnecting the affected systems, devices, or networks, changing the passwords or access codes, or deleting or recovering the data. The project also investigates and analyzes the data breach, using various techniques, such as forensic analysis, root cause analysis, or incident response analysis, to identify and address the source and the scope of the breach.

- **Notification:** The project notifies and informs the relevant parties and authorities of the data breach, using various methods, such as email, phone, or letter, depending on the urgency and the severity of the breach. The project also complies with the GDPR and other relevant data protection regulations, ensuring that the data breach notification is done within 72 hours of becoming aware of the breach. The project also provides the following information in the data breach notification: the nature and extent of the data breach, the type, volume, and sensitivity of the data involved, the cause and duration of the breach, the potential impact and harm of the breach, the measures taken to contain and mitigate the breach, the contact details of the data manager, and the advice and guidance for the data subjects or providers on how to protect themselves from the breach.

10. Conclusions

This document has presented the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the RE-INTEGRATE project, which aims to develop climate-compatible energy strategies through collaboration between the African Union and the European Union. The DMP outlines the project's data management practices, ensuring that the data is handled, shared, and preserved in alignment with the project's objectives and the FAIR data principles. The DMP also addresses the ethical and legal aspects of data management, complying with the GDPR and other data protection regulations, and respecting the rights and interests of the data subjects and providers. The DMP is a living document, which will be reviewed and updated throughout the project lifecycle, adapting to the changing needs and findings of the project. Two updated versions of the DMP will be delivered to the European Commission in M18 (D6.5, Data Management Plan V2) and in M30 (D6.6, Data Management Plan V3).

The DMP plays a pivotal role in the RE-INTEGRATE project, ensuring the effective management of data crucial for achieving the project's goals of fostering shared knowledge and collaborative advancements in energy strategies across the EU and AU. The DMP directly supports the project's delineated objectives, including formalizing partnerships across national energy planning ecosystems, conducting integrated assessments for climate-compatible energy development strategies, formulating actionable policy recommendations, establishing a robust monitoring and evaluation framework for knowledge sharing, and developing a comprehensive dissemination, communication, and exploitation mechanism. These objectives collectively aim to enhance research quality and impact, emphasizing the creation of reliable, relevant, and reusable data that contributes significantly to the scientific and societal understanding in the energy and climate domain. Furthermore, the DMP facilitates the broad sharing and dissemination of data, ensuring it is accessible and interoperable for a diverse audience of stakeholders, thereby promoting mutual learning and exchange between the EU and AU. By adhering to the DMP, the RE-INTEGRATE project aspires to significantly improve energy strategies through enhanced collaboration between the AU and EU, reflecting a commitment to climate compatibility and alignment with the specific objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement.

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